

Post Colonial Perspectives in Badal Sircar's Indian History Made Easy

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Abstract

Badal Sircar is the most Prolific playwright of the post-Independence period. He has written and published many street plays in Bengali. His plays portay the very minute aspects and themes of post colonialism. He discloses the pathetic condition of the contemporary society in his plays. He founded the new form of theater called the "Street Theater". Badal Sircar as a playwright has his chief focus and attention on post colonialism. He discusses about its impacts on our country through his plays that are written in fragments without any connection. Badal Sircar has focused on the colonial rule of the British in India in Indian History Made Easy. British came in to India during the Mughal period in the name of business. The British got permission to do business in India. Gradually, the British got a strong hold of our country by controlling the economic and political systems of India. They imposed their traditional, cultural, political and economic values on the colonised in India during the colonial period which had created a negative impact in the lives of the Indians even in the post colonial era.

Keywords: British Colonial rule, Hegemony, Colonisers, Colonised, Ruling Class, Subordinate Class.

The British rule is considered to be the worst rule because of the damages it caused to all the political, financial, social and psychological systems in India whereas the other rulers like Mughals, Aryans were beneficial and not harmful to the country. Since the Mughals gave permission to the British to conduct business in the seventeenth century, Sircar calls it the dark period of Bharat's history in the play. The Mughal emperor Jahangir is entirely responsible for the British colonial rule in India. Kulsoom Fatima states in her "Postcolonial Content in the Plays of Badal Sircar": "Through this play Sircar has successfully delineated the nature of exploitation and trickeries played by colonial oppressors on Indian natives during colonial period" (213). Sircar also wants to praise the positive side of the Mughal rule in India. Because the Indian villages flourished well and the people in the villages live a self sufficient life each. The revenue tax paid by the farmers, potters and weavers were so reasonable and were directly paid to the king.

As India is a country of rich natural resources, the British made a very good use of it. They paid Silver worth 30,000 Sterling pounds to the India for doing business every year. "Took clothes-cotton, silk, muslin, and benarasi. . . Took iron, brass material. . . Took what not!" (8). In return they gave ". . . silver worth 30,000 sterling pound-s to India every year" (IHME 10).

After the battle of Plassey in 1757, during the Governor Generalship of Robert Clive, the Nawab of the smaller kingdoms of India had become the puppet in the hands of the East India Company. After it, the British found it easy to buy any good at the cheapest rate in Indian market and at the same time the company sells their goods at an extremely high rate. In *Indian History Made Easy*, the Governor General informs Mother Britannia, "There's no need to worry now. Silver's needed no more. Got dewani of Bengal, Bihar, and Orissa. The Nawab's puppet in our hands. What we'll buy-we'll buy for a penny. But sell at a price that's four times" (11). Moreover they levied and inflicted heavy taxes on the Indians

30 September 1765. Respected Directors. It is expected that your company will be able to extract revenue worth two and half crore of sicca rupees this year on account of the dewani of Bengal, Bihar and Orissa. Later it will increase by twenty to thirty lakh in a year. . . . Therefore there is a net profit of one crore twenty-two lakh of sicca rupees or sixteen lakh fifty thousand nine hundred sterling pound-s. Your, Robert Clive. (12)

Due to the unbearable taxes imposed on the weavers, potter etc., has a deep impact and effect on them. They could not earn any profit out of their business and so they decided to move to the village and become peasants in the golden rule of Jahangir who concentrated much on the development of the villages and agriculture. But in the village, the Zamindar was made the owner of the land by the East India Company whereas it was owned by the common people in the village earlier.

During the colonial era, in the seventeenth century, one third of the farming land turned into forest because of Zamindari system practiced by the colonizers in the villages. They collected taxes from both the landlords and landless, poverty stricken farmers in an equal manner. During the Governor Generalship of Lord Cornwallis, he introduced a Permanent Settlement policy for the revenue tax which aimed at exploiting the peasants or farmers.

Lord Cornwallis introduced a new revenue system under the permanent settlement of Bengal in 1793 with a view to stabilize land revenue and create a loyal contented class of Zamindars. This abolished periodic auction of Zamindari rights and established permanent Zamindari rights to collect land revenue from the tenants and payment of a fixed amount to Government treasury every year"

Peasants who also own a land of their own turned out to be the tenants due to famine. Zamindars and the rich land lords were given the power to kick the peasants at any time. Peasants are exploited to the core and they are used only as servants or slaves by the Government through the Zamindars. In *Indian History Made Easy*, Sircar conveys that there were thirty one famines in 125 years from 1776 to 1900 in India. Due to famine, about thirty million Indian died. During the third period of British colonization, "Industrial capital was changed to Financial capital" (31) pg 144 and it is made evident by Sircar in the play.

The Sepoy Mutiny of 1857 rebelled against the British rule in the disguise of East India Company and it ended the rule of it. The Sepoy Mutiny was a violent and very bloody uprising against British rule in India in 1857. So the Sepoy Mutiny' uprisals were punished by the British colonizers in a very harsh and cruel manner. The Sepoy Mutiny ended the rule of East India Company and India came under the rule of British queen. The Britain's tactics of monopolization of the Indian markets was the one of the major reason of the First World War.

After the First World War some anti liberation movement emerged in India and they started to demand Independence at the time in August 1917 Edwin Samuel Montague was the British liberal

politician. He was a radical liberal and the third practicing Jew to serve in the British cabinet. Montague announced that the aim of British rule in India is to concentrate in “The gradual development of self governing institutions with a view to the progressive realization of the responsible government in India as an Integral part of the British Empire”

In the colonial India many Indians were educated according to the ideas imposed by the British government in the field of education. British colonizers called these educated people as their children on the intellectual ground because the methods, facts and the culture involved in the education was completely westernized. Our Indian languages were pushed down and English played a dominant role as an official language from those days till today. The colonizers had also corrupted some rich and fortunate Indians who were “Zamindars, money lenders, brokers, Babus.” The fortunate natives stood by the side of the colonizers in order to cheat and grab unbearable revenue and land taxes, from their fellow people which had pushed the major parts of India to the poverty line.

According to Sircar the Second World War made British become weakened, because of the people’s protest against capitalism and the Quit India Movement or the India August Movement. It was a movement launched on 8th August 1942 during World War II and it demanded an end to the British Raj of India. Though in 1947, India was liberated and become independent out the impact of colonialism left an enduring and undying marks on the Indian Society Culture politics and economy.

Sircar concludes the play with the point that though India has become Independent with wealth, prosperity, happiness and development in the lives of the people, there is discrimination based on race, caste, sex and religion and violence. Sircar feels that in equality, lust for job power, money and reputation are found everywhere in the post colonial India.

Sircar seems to be very much influenced by Karl Marx’s writings while writing Indian History Made Easy. Though Karl Marx is strongly against capitalism, he has never attempted to criticize or attack capitalism in a frank manner. The colonizers used the colonial expansion to develop their capital.

Sircar never failed in reviling capitalism in the needed situations. But after the first war of Indian Independence, Indian came directly into the hands of the British Queen. The Queen stood strongly in favour of capitalism and ordered her sons to increase factories, labourer, products or goods and especially the banks so that they can increase their capital and the manufacture of goods and commodities. The queen directed her sons to go to the far off villages, forests, mountains and deserts to sell the commodities.

The prohibition of socialist revolution which is necessary to bring about structural changes in the society and to bring transition from capitalism to socialism is very much favorable to the elite or the bourgeoisie. Because they find it easy to exploit the lower class and poor people and have easily damaged the Indian social and economic systems immensely.

In the play, Sircar has made it evident, “Millions of efficient Indian artisans are unemployed!”, “The population of Dhaka goes down from two hundred thousand to thirty thousand!” and “The unemployed artisans move to the villages in groups. They have become peasants” (Sircar, IHME 26). Thus, readers can understand that the industrial revolution that took place in modern colonial era has pushed the lower, working class below the status and level of human beings and used them as instruments or tools to overlook the machine work to produce capital. In order to increase their capital, it is essential to create a economic imbalance in the colonized country. The British had done it in a very clever manner in the disguise of free trade and East India Company. They have totally caused destruction to the Indian economic system and had got hold of their business and increased their capital.

Hegemony is an important feature of the post colonial studies and it is made clearly visible in the play *Indian History Made Easy*. Hegemony is,

. . . initially a term referring to the dominance of one state within a confederation, is now generally understood to mean domination by consent. This broader meaning was coined and popularized in the 1930s by Italian Marxist Antonio Gramsci, who investigated why the ruling class was so successful in promoting its own interests in society. Fundamentally, hegemony is the power of the ruling class to convince other classes that their interests are the interests of all. Domination is thus exerted not by force, nor even necessarily by active persuasion, but by a more subtle and inclusive power over the economy, and over state apparatuses such as education and the media, by which the ruling class's interest is presented as the common interest and thus comes to be taken for granted. . . . Hegemony is important because the capacity to influence the thought of the colonized is by far the most sustained and potent operation of imperial power in colonized regions. (Ashcroft, Griffiths, and Tiffin, *Post-Colonial Studies* 116)

Hegemony is an important post colonial characteristic that gives economic and political power to the elite ruling class to rule and dominate the subordinate class. The ruling class persuades the working class and convinces them by declaring that the heads and concerns of the former should be the interests of all. The elite class exercises the dominance over subordinate class by brilliant persuasion and not by power. Sircar has highlighted "Hegemony" as the theme in *Indian History Made Easy*.

Due to the establishment of big factories the Indian markets were flooded with factory and machine made goods and commodities. The Indian cottage industry products were not able to compete with those goods. Moreover the natives were very much attracted and yielded towards the factory goods and not the hand made goods. Due to these facts, many efficient artisans, weavers gold smiths, blacksmiths were directed to work in fields and do agriculture. When the plight of these unemployed Indian workers was questioned, Mother Britannia replied thus in *Indian History Made Easy*. "They'll work in the fields. India is an agricultural country. This is history. . . . From today onwards. With time, the Indians will believe it too. My sonny will make them believe. My son, my child, my lululululu!" (24). Thus the readers can understand the British's hold over the Indian economy through which they hegemonise the native Indians.

The colonizers extended the hegemony to the next phase of interpellation in which the former made the colonized accept the imperial culture, beliefs and Eurocentric values to be superior and the native culture and tradition to be inferior. Moreover, interpellation is imperial processes in which the imperialists make the colonized accept their marginality and the colonial superiority of the rulers. Hegemony served the British as a good beneficial factor.

The political control of the ex-colonised country in the hands of the colonized and the economic control of the ex-colonised country in the hands of the ex-colonisers is called as neocolonialism. Like hegemony, neocolonialism is also a significant feature of post colonial studies. Neocolonialism is defined by Khume Nkrumah in 1961. According to Nkrumah the Indian Independence is deceitful and ambiguous, because it gives only political possession of the country to the native and not the economic possession of the country. Neo-colonialism is understood to be the modern imperialism.

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